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IMPLEMENTATION OF MODULAR INSTRUCTION UNDER NEW NORMAL AT JESUS S. CABARRUS ELEMENTARY SCHOOL: STRATEGIES, STATUS, AND CONCERNS

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ABSTRACT

Title: IMPLEMENTATION OF MODULAR INSTRUCTION UNDER NEW NORMAL AT JESUS S. CABARRUS ELEMENTARY SCHOOL: STRATEGIES, STATUS, AND CONCERNS

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School: JESUS S. CABARRUS ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

Principal: DR. EVANGELINE R. QUIBUYEN

Learning is a continuous process amidst COVID-19 pandemic. Face-to-face classes shifted to flexible learning wherein some public schools undergo modular distance learning to continue providing quality teaching-learning processes of education to learners. The study aims to determine the strategies, status, and concerns encountered in implementing modular instruction amidst the COVID-19 crisis. The study was conducted to improve strategies executed in terms of the modular distance learning program of the institution amidst the pandemic. This qualitative research method developed and utilized a survey questionnaire distributed to seventy-four (74) teachers – advisers, seventy-four (74) selected pupils from Grade 4 to Grade 6, and seventy-four (74) parents coming from different sections.

Based on the findings in the strategies on module distribution, teachers, parents and pupils perceived that scheduled distribution and retrieval of printed copy at school were interpreted as Agree while in module instructions provision available for monitoring the works of pupils through online kumustahan with sufficient advice and guidance from the teacher was interpreted as agree, and lastly for module checking, as for teachers it is Strongly Agree strategy to check module

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weekly, and for parents and pupils, check modules with teachers feedback helped them to learn more, it is interpreted as Agree. It is perceived by the teachers, parents and pupils, the importance of teachers' role, parents' role, and pupils' role in the implementation of modular instruction with respective means of 4.850, 4.207, and 4.5391. In terms of challenges faced during the implementation of the modular instruction, the pasabay scheme was a challenge for the teacher and lots of works to be done aside from checking. And for perception of parents and pupils, in the implementation of modular instruction was lots of activities and performance are needed to comply. Teachers' role, parents' role, and pupil role were all essential in the implementation of modular instruction. On these findings, the researchers recommend the sustainability and continuous implementation of the modular instruction for the next school year. Furthermore, the researcher recommend an action plan. as the basis of implementation of the modular instructions amidst the pandemic for the school year 2022 - 2023.

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